

Searching for number-conserving non-uniform binary cellular automata

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Abstract. We consider one-dimensional cellular automata whose cells can use different local rules to update their states. We study such cellular automata on the infinite grid and on its subgrids in the context of number conservation.

Keywords: Cellular automata · non-uniform cellular automata · number conservation.

We investigate non-uniform CAs (ν -CAs), *i.e.*, one-dimensional CAs acting on the infinite grid (or on some of its subgrids), for which cells can use different local rules to update their states. The infinite grid is denoted by $\mathcal{G}_{-\infty}^{\infty}$, *i.e.*

$$\mathcal{G}_{-\infty}^{\infty} = \{\dots, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots\}.$$

Additionally, we consider the following subgrids of $\mathcal{G}_{-\infty}^{\infty}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{G}_{-\infty}^n &= \{\dots, n-2, n-1, n\}, \text{ for } n \in \mathbb{Z}; \\ \mathcal{G}_m^{\infty} &= \{m, m+1, m+2, \dots\}, \text{ for } m \in \mathbb{Z}; \\ \mathcal{G}_m^n &= \{m, m+1, \dots, n-1, n\}, \text{ for } m, n \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ satisfying } m \leq n.\end{aligned}$$

If the type of the considered grid is irrelevant, we simply use the symbol \mathcal{G} , as this should not lead to confusion.

A configuration is any function from the grid \mathcal{G} to the binary state set $\{0, 1\}$ and the set of all configurations is denoted by X . The value at a cell $i \in \mathcal{G}$ in a configuration $\mathbf{x} \in X$ is denoted by x_i . Most often, a configuration $\mathbf{x} \in X$ is conveniently represented as a sequence $(x_i)_{i \in \mathcal{G}}$

For a configuration \mathbf{x} , we denote by $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ the sum of all states in \mathbf{x} , *i.e.*, $\mu(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{G}} x_i$. A configuration \mathbf{x} is said to be *finite* if the number of cells i for which $x_i = 1$ is finite (*i.e.*, if $\mu(\mathbf{x}) < +\infty$).

Let \mathcal{S} be a finite set of binary local rules. Each rule sequence $[f_i]_{i \in \mathcal{G}}$, where $f_i \in \mathcal{S}$ for any $i \in \mathcal{G}$, induces a ν -CA $H : X \rightarrow X$ defined by, for any $\mathbf{x} \in X$ and $i \in \mathcal{G}$:

$$H(\mathbf{x})_i = f_i(x_{i-1}, x_i, x_{i+1}), \quad (1)$$

with the convention that if $j \notin \mathcal{G}$ we use *null boundary conditions* and in the case of finite subgrids also *periodic boundary conditions*.

The main property of ν -CAs that is investigated in our research is *number conservation*. In the binary case, it states that a given ν -CA preserves the number of ones in any finite configuration throughout its evolution.

Definition 1. *A ν -CA H on \mathcal{G} is called number-conserving if $\mu(H(\mathbf{x})) = \mu(\mathbf{x})$ for each finite configuration $\mathbf{x} \in X$.*

Let us note that the above definition is one of two ones being considered for the infinite grid, however, in the case of the ν -CAs considered by us, both of them are equivalent (see Proposition 1 in [1]).

At the beginning of the research, we focused on to the so-called **non-uniform elementary** CAs (ν -ECAs), in which each cell is allowed to have its own local updating rule belonging to Wolfram's set of 256 elementary local rules. In our previous paper [2], we managed to describe in detail all number-conserving ν -ECAs on finite grids both with periodic and null boundary conditions. The main result of [2] states that each number-conserving ν -ECA on a finite grid of length at least five cells (regardless of the boundary conditions: periodic or null) is either a classical (uniform) number-conserving ECA or it is a conglomerate of components, which can be of four different types only and each of them has a very poor dynamics. Moreover, each component of the conglomerate "lives its own life", as if there were impermeable barriers between adjacent components. The characterization obtained allows, *inter alia*, to enumerate all number-conserving ν -ECAs on finite grids and and those that are reversible. Surprisingly, the numbers obtained are closely related to the Fibonacci sequence.

Since the structure of the number-conserving ν -ECAs does not change with the increase of the grid (no matter how long the considered grid is, all number-conserving ν -ECAs on it are built with the same four mentioned types of components), one might erroneously conclude that the same would be true of the infinite grid. Of course, all examples of number-conserving ν -ECAs found for finite grids can be, in some way, "converted" to the infinite grid. It turns out, however, that the infinite grid admits many other types of number-conserving ν -ECAs (see [3]). This means that when considering number conservation for non-uniform cellular automata, the infinite grid cannot be treated as a limiting case of finite grids, *i.e.*, there are number-conserving non-uniform cellular automata on the infinite grid that have no analogous counterpart on finite grids. Thus, unfortunately, computer experiments are useless to assist in finding these other types.

Now we try to describe what all ν -CAs look like if we increase the radius to $3/2$. Right from the start, we are faced with an incredibly great computational complexity, even if we only consider finite grids. However, we were able to obtain some promising results that give hope for solving this problem in the future.

References

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